

Some Characterizations of General s-Convex Functions

Mohammed .A. Osman Tom

1- Department of Mathematics , Faculty of Science, University of Tabuk , PO Box 4279 ,
Tabuk-7491, Saudi Arabia.

Abstract. It is established that the general s-Convex function are a new class of generalized convex functions. In a similar ven a new class of general s-convex sets is introduced which are generalizations of s-convex set. It is shown that radially lower semicontinuous function $h: N \rightarrow R \cup \{+\infty\}$ is general s-convex if and only if , for all $b_1, b_2 \in N$ there exist $\sigma = (b_1, b_2) \in (0,1)$ that satisfies

$$h(\sigma b_1 + (1 - \sigma)b_2) \leq \sigma^s [(h(b_1)) + \delta(b_1, \sigma)] + (1 - \sigma)^s [h(b_2) + \delta(b_2, \sigma)] + \delta\left(\frac{b_1+b_2}{2}, \sigma\right)$$

holds $\forall b_1, b_2 \in P, \sigma \in [1,0]$ and for some fixed $s \in (0,1)$.

Keywords. General s-convex set , General s-convex function , Inequality.

1. Introduction

Due to significance of convexity and generalized convexity , researches focused heavily on the generalized convex functions. For instance , Earlier works by H.Hudzik et, al .[9] presented two types of s-convexity $\{s \in (0,1)\}$, the second notion is fundamentally stronger than the s-convexity in the first sense. E-convex sets and E-convex functions are a class of sets and a class of functions introduced by Youness [6]. Functions by loosening up how convex sets and convex functions are defined. X.M. Yang [22] offered a few instance for E.A.paper [6] , by Youness and improved it .More findings about generalized E-convex functions , locations cites [6] , [3].A generalization of semi-preinvex functions and b-vex functions is known as semi-preinvex functions. A class of functions known as E-b-vex functions which is defined as an extension of b-vex functions and E-vex functions , was introduced by Yu-Rn Syau et, al [22].A new family of functions known as approximately b-invex functions was studied by Emam [20] , some of the characteristics were explored , and suitable optimality requirements for nonlinear programming utilising these functions were obtained. A family of sub-b-convex sets and novel generalized these sub-b-convex were examined by M.T.Chao et,al. in 2012 [16], who also provided the necessary conditions for the optimality of both unconstrained and inequality –constrained sub-b-convex programming. For more details on generalized convex functions can be found in [18],[4].Through their researches , generalized convex functions like the b-invex function were developed. In the meantime , we now discover a class of generalized convex functions that is more comprehensive than the types of generalized convex functions and which is not sub-b-convex but which shares some of their characteristics. Because sub-b-convexity and s-convexity are extensions of convexity.In this paper we established a new concepts of general s-convex function by motivated definitions of sub-b-convexity , s-convexity and sub-b-s-convexity of function. On the other hand we proved that a lower semi-continuous function radially lower semicontinuous function $h: D \rightarrow R \cup \{+\infty\}$ is general s-convex if and only if , for all $b_1, b_2 \in D$ there exist $\sigma = (b_1, b_2) \in (0,1)$ that satisfies

$$h(\sigma b_1 + (1 - \sigma)b_2) \leq \sigma^s [(h(b_1)) + \delta(b_1, \sigma)] + (1 - \sigma)^s [h(b_2) + \delta(b_2, \sigma)] + \delta\left(\frac{b_1+b_2}{2}, \sigma\right)$$

holds $\forall b_1, b_2 \in P, \sigma \in [1,0]$ and for some fixed $s \in (0,1)$.

2. Basic Results

We reviewed the definitions of sub-b-convexity, s -convexity and sub-b- s -convexity of function at beginning of this section. According to M.T.Chao et al [6], the class of sub-b-convex function is as follows. Let $\aleph$ be a convex set in R^m which is nonempty throughout the entire paper.

Definition 2.1. [6] A real-valued function h on $\aleph$ w.r.t the map $b: \aleph \times \aleph \times [1,0] \rightarrow R$ is known to be sub-b-convex if

$$h(\sigma b_1 + (1 - \sigma)b_2) \leq \sigma h(b_1) + (1 - \sigma)h(b_2) + (b_1, b_2, \sigma)$$

holds $\forall b_1, b_2 \in P, \sigma \in [1,0]$.

Definition 2.2. [1] A real-valued function h on $\aleph$ is known to be s -convex in second sense if

$$h(\sigma b_1 + (1 - \sigma)b_2) < \sigma^s h(b_1) + (1 - \sigma)^s h(b_2)$$

holds $\forall b_1, b_2 \in P, \sigma \in [1,0]$ and for some fixed $s \in (1,0]$.

Definition 2.3. [9] A real-valued function h on $\aleph$ w.r.t the map $b: \aleph \times \aleph \times [1,0] \rightarrow R$ is known to be sub-b- s -convex in second sense if

$$h(\sigma b_1 + (1 - \sigma)b_2) < \sigma^s h(b_1) + (1 - \sigma)^s h(b_2) + (b_1, b_2, \sigma)$$

holds $\forall b_1, b_2 \in P, \sigma \in [1,0]$ and for some fixed $s \in (1,0]$.

Motivated by definitions 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3 we give the new concepts of general s -convex function which is given below.

Definition 2.4. A real-valued function h on $\aleph$ w.r.t the function $\delta: \aleph \times [1,0] \rightarrow R$ is known to be general s -convex if

$$h(\sigma b_1 + (1 - \sigma)b_2) \leq \sigma^s [(h(b_1)) + \delta(b_1, \sigma)] + (1 - \sigma)^s [h(b_2) + \delta(b_2, \sigma)] + \delta\left(\frac{b_1 + b_2}{2}, \sigma\right) \quad (2.1)$$

holds $\forall b_1, b_2 \in P, \sigma \in [1,0]$ and for some fixed $s \in (1,0]$.

Remark 2.1. If we take $\delta(b_1, \sigma) = 0$, then general s -convex function becomes s -convex in the second sense. On the other hand, if we take $\delta(b_1, \sigma) = 0$ and $s = 1$, then general s -convex function becomes convex.

Theorem 2.5. Suppose that $h_1, h_2: \aleph \rightarrow R$ are general s -convex function w.r.t. the same map

$\delta: \aleph \times [1,0] \rightarrow R$, then $h_1 + h_2$ and $\alpha h_1 (\alpha \geq 0)$ are general s -convex functions w.r.t. the same map.

Corollary 2.5.1. Suppose that $h_k: \aleph \rightarrow R, (k = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ are general s -convex function w.r.t. the same map. $\delta_k: \aleph \times [1,0] \rightarrow R, (k = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ respectively, then the function

$$h = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k h_k, (\alpha_k \geq 0), (k = 1, 2, \dots, n)$$

is general s-convex function w.r.t. the same map. $\delta = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k \delta_k, (k = 1, 2, \dots, n)$

Proposition 2.6. Suppose that $h_k: \mathfrak{N} \rightarrow R, (k = 1, 2, 3 \dots, n)$ are general s-convex function w.r.t. the same map. $\delta_k: \mathfrak{N} \times [1,0] \rightarrow R, (k = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ respectively, then the function $h = \max\{h_i = k = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ is general s-convex function w.r.t. the same map $\delta = \max\{\delta_i = k = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$.

Theorem 2.7. Suppose that $h_1: \mathfrak{N} \rightarrow R$, are general s-convex function w.r.t. the same map $\delta: \mathfrak{N} \times [1,0] \rightarrow R$ and the another function $h_2: R \rightarrow R$ which is linear as well as non-decreasing, then $h_2 \circ h_1$ is a general s-convex function w.r.t. the same map $h_2 \circ \delta$.
Now we introduced a new theory of general s-convex set as below.

Definition 2.8. Assume $\mathfrak{N}_1$ be a non-empty subset of R^{m+1} . Then, the set $\mathfrak{N}$ is known to be general s-convex set w.r.t. the same map $\delta: R^m \times [1,0] \rightarrow R$, if

$$\left(\sigma b_1 + (1 - \sigma)b_2, \sigma^s [\alpha + \delta(b_1, \sigma) + (1 - \sigma)^s \beta + \delta(b_2, \sigma)] + \delta\left(\frac{b_1 + b_2}{2}, \sigma\right) \right) \in \mathfrak{N}$$

holds $\forall (b_1, \alpha), (b_2, \beta) \in \mathfrak{N}_1, b_1, b_2 \in R^m, \sigma \in [1,0]$ and for some fixed $s \in (1,0]$.

Here, we characterise the general s-convex function in terms of their epigraph $E(\mathfrak{N})$ which is provided by

$$E(\mathfrak{N}) = \{(b, \beta) : b \in \mathfrak{N}, \beta \in R, h(b) \leq \beta\}$$

Theorem 2.9. A function $h: \mathfrak{N} \rightarrow R$ is a general s-convex w.r.t. the same map $\delta: \mathfrak{N} \times [1,0] \rightarrow R$, $\Leftrightarrow E(\mathfrak{N})$ is a general s-convex set w.r.t. the same map δ

Proposition 2.10. Let us suppose that $\mathfrak{N}_i$ is a family of general s-convex set w.r.t. the same map δ then $\cap_{i \in I} \mathfrak{N}_i$ is also a general s-convex set w.r.t. the same map δ .

Proof. Take $(b_1, \beta_1), (b_2, \beta_2) \in \cap_{i \in I} \mathfrak{N}_i$, then, for any $i \in I, (b_1, \beta_1), (b_2, \beta_2) \in \mathfrak{N}_i$. As $\mathfrak{N}_i$ is a general s-convex set w.r.t. the same map δ , for some $s \in (1,0]$ and $\forall \sigma \in [1,0]$ it demonstrate that

$$\left(\sigma b_1 + (1 - \sigma)b_2, \sigma^s [\beta_1 + \delta(b_1, \sigma) + (1 - \sigma)^s [\beta_2 + \delta(b_2, \sigma)]] + \delta\left(\frac{b_1 + b_2}{2}, \sigma\right) \right) \in \mathfrak{N}_i$$

For any $i \in I$. Hence

$$\left(\sigma b_1 + (1 - \sigma)b_2, \sigma^s [\beta_1 + \delta(b_1, \sigma) + (1 - \sigma)^s [\beta_2 + \delta(b_2, \sigma)]] + \delta\left(\frac{b_1 + b_2}{2}, \sigma\right) \right) \in \cap_{i \in I} \mathfrak{N}_i$$

Therefore $\cap_{i \in I} \mathfrak{N}_i$ is a general s-convex set w.r.t. map δ and the proof is completed.

Proposition 2.11. If $\{h_i = i \in K\}$ is a collection of arbitrary functions and all h_i is a general s-convex function w.r.t. the common map δ , then the arbitrary function $h = \sup_{i \in I} h_i(b_1)$ is a general s-convex function w.r.t. the common map δ .

3 Main Results

Theorem 3.1. Let D be a convex subset of a real vector space. Then , a radially lower semi-continuous function $h: D \rightarrow R \cup \{+\infty\}$ is a general s -convex if and only if for all $b_1, b_2 \in D$ There exists $\sigma = (b_1, b_2) \in (1,0)$ that satisfies inequality (2,1).

Corollary 3.2. Let $D \subseteq R$ be a nonempty interval , then a lower semi-continuous function $h: D \rightarrow R \cup \{+\infty\}$ is a general s -convex if and only if for all $b_1, b_2 \in D$ There exist $\sigma = (b_1, b_2) \in (1,0)$ that satisfies inequality (2,1).It is worth nothing that the lower semi-continuous assumption cannot be relaxed too much since there exists a nonconvex function $h: D \rightarrow R \cup \{+\infty\}$ that is lower semi-continuous everywhere in D except at countably many point and such , for all $b_1, b_2 \in D$ there exists $\sigma = (b_1, b_2) \in (1,0)$ that satisfies inequality (2,1).Indeed , it is sufficient to choose $D = R$ and let h be indicator function of the rationals , i.e , $h(b_1) = 1$ if b_1 is rational and $h(b_1) = 0$ otherwise.

Proof of theorem 3.1.

We need to prove the if "part ". More over , the claim is obvious that if D is empty , hence let us suppose that $D \neq \emptyset$. Fixed $b_1, b_2 \in D$ and define set

$$M = \left\{ \sigma \in [1,0]; h(\sigma b_1 + (1 - \sigma)b_2) \leq \sigma^s [(h(b_1)) + \delta(b_1, \sigma)] + (1 - \sigma)^s [h(b_2) + \delta(b_2, \sigma)] + \delta\left(\frac{b_1 + b_2}{2}, \sigma\right) \right\}$$

Note that $M = [1,0]$ provided that $h(b_1) < +\infty$ and $h(b_2) < +\infty$

Claim 1. M is a nonempty compact subset of $[1,0]$

Proof. Note that $\{1,0\} \subseteq M \subseteq [1,0]$, hence M is nonempty and bounded.

Let (σ_n) be a sequence in M such that $\sigma_n \uparrow \sigma > 0$. Define the real sequence (t_n) by $t_n := 1 - \frac{\sigma_n}{\sigma}$ for each n and note that $t_n \downarrow 0$. Since h is radially lower semi-continuous, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} & h(\sigma b_1 + (1 - \sigma)b_2) \\ & \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} h[\sigma^s(b_1) + \delta(b_1, \sigma)] \\ & \quad + \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} h[(1 - \sigma)^s(b_2) + \delta(b_2, \sigma)] + \delta\left(\frac{b_1 + b_2}{2}, \sigma\right) \\ & \quad + t_n(b_2 - \sigma b_1 - (1 - \sigma)b_2) \\ = & \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} h[\sigma_n^s(b_1) + \delta(b_1, \sigma_n)] \\ & \quad + \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} h[(1 - \sigma_n)^s(b_2) + \delta(b_2, \sigma_n)] + \delta\left(\frac{b_1 + b_2}{2}, \sigma_n\right) \\ = & \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} h(\sigma_n b_1 + (1 - \sigma_n)b_2) \\ \leq & \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} h \sigma_n h(b_1) + (1 - \sigma_n)h(b_2) \\ = & \sigma h(b_1) + (1 - \sigma)h(b_2) \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, given (σ_n) in M such that $\sigma_n \downarrow \sigma < 1$, let (M_n) be the sequence defined by

$M_n := \frac{1-\sigma_n}{1-\sigma}$ for each n and note that $M_n \downarrow 0$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & h(\sigma b_1 + (1 - \sigma)b_2) \\ & \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} h[\sigma^s(b_1) + \delta(b_1, \sigma)] \\ & \quad + \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} h[(1 - \sigma)^s(b_2) + \delta(b_2, \sigma)] + \delta\left(\frac{b_1 + b_2}{2}, \sigma\right) \\ & \quad + M_n(b_1 - \sigma b_1 - (1 - \sigma)b_2) \\ & = \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} h h(\sigma_n b_1 + (1 - \sigma_n)b_2) \leq \sigma h(b_1) + (1 - \sigma)h(b_2) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore M is also closed, proving the claim.

Claim 2. $(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) \cap M \neq \emptyset, \forall \sigma_1, \sigma_2 \in M$ with $\sigma_1 < \sigma_2$ (note that this is possible since $\{1,0\} \subseteq M$) and define $k = \sigma_1 b_1 + (1 - \sigma_1)b_2$ and $g = \sigma_2 b_1 + (1 - \sigma_2)b_2$

Hence $k, g \in D$ and by hypothesis, there exist

$\sigma = \sigma(k, g) \in (1,0)$ such that

$$h(\sigma k + (1 - \sigma)g) \leq \sigma^s[(h(k)) + \delta(k, \sigma)] + (1 - \sigma)^s[h(g) + \delta(g, \sigma)] + \delta\left(\frac{k+g}{2}, \sigma\right)$$

at this point, define $\sigma' = \sigma\sigma_1 + (1 - \sigma)\sigma_2$ and observe that

$$\begin{aligned} & h(\sigma' b_1 + (1 - \sigma')b_2) = h(\sigma k + (1 - \sigma)g) \\ & \leq \sigma h(k) + (1 - \sigma)h(g) \\ & \leq \sigma(\sigma_1 h(b_1) + (1 - \sigma_1)h(b_2) + (1 - \sigma)(\sigma_2 h(b_1) + (1 - \sigma_2)h(b_2))) \\ & = \sigma' h(b_1) + (1 - \sigma')h(b_2) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\sigma' \in M$. Then the claim follows by the fact that $\sigma_1 < \sigma' < \sigma_2$

To complete the proof of Theorem 3.1, let us suppose for the sake of contraction that

$$\Lambda := [1,0] \setminus M \neq \emptyset.$$

Note that Λ is open since it can be written as $(1,0) \cap M^c$ and M^c is open by Claim 1.

Fixed $\sigma \in \Lambda$. Hence, there is a maximal open interval (σ_1, σ_2) and containing σ and in Λ .

Then $\sigma_1, \sigma_2 \in M$ while $(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) \cap M = \emptyset$, contradicting Claim2.

This shows that h is necessarily a general s-convex function.

4. Conclusion.

In this paper we introduced a new concept of general s-convex function and we observed that this concept of general s-convex function can be reduce to s-convex in the second sense if we take $\delta(b_1, \sigma) = 0$ and can be reduced to convex function if we take $\delta(b_1, \sigma) = 0$ and $s = 1$.

Acknowledgments. The author is grateful to editor and two anonymous referees for their remarks that allowed a substantial improvement of the presentation.

References

- [1] H.Hudzik and L.Maligranda , Some remarks on s-convex functions . *Aequationes mathematicae* , 48(1) , (1994),pp.47-58.
- [2] E.A. Youness, E-convex sets ,E-convex functions , and E-convex Programming *Journal of Optimization Theory and Applications* , 102(2) , (1999), pp.439-450.
- [3] C. Fulga and V. Preda, Nonlinear Programming with E-preinvex and local E-preinvex functions. *European Journal of Operational Research* , 192(3), (2009), pp.737-743.
- [4] X.M. Yang, On E-convex sets , E-convex functions, and E-convex programming , *Journal of Optimization Theory and Applications* , 109(3), (2001), p.699.
- [5] T. Emam. Roughly B-invex Programming problems .*Calcolo*, 48(2), (2011), pp.173-188.
- [6] M.T. Chao, J.B. Jain , D.Y. Liang, Sub-b-convex functions and Sub-b-convex programming, *Operations Research Transactions (China)* 16 , (2012), pp.1-8.
- [7] S.K.Mishra , R.N. Mohapatra and E.A. Youness , Some properties of semi E-b-vex functions. *Applied mathematics and Computation*, 217 (12) , (2011), pp.5525-5530.
- [8] C. Zălinescu , A critical view on invexity , *Journal of Optimization Theory and Application* ,162(3), (2014), pp.695-704.
- [9] J. Liao and T. Du ,On Some Characterizations of Sub-b-s-convex functions. *Filomat*,30(14), (2016),pp3885-3895.